

A Comparative Analysis of Bayesian Optimization and Traditional Hyperparameter Optimization Methods: A Survey

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ABSTRACT

Hyperparameter optimization (HPO) enhances machine learning models by selecting optimal hyperparameter configurations. In deep learning (DL), multi-layered neural networks automatically learn hierarchical features, and efficient HPO techniques improve accuracy, convergence, and generalization of DL models while reducing computational costs. Traditional HPO methods, such as grid search and random search, are straightforward but often inefficient due to exhaustive or uninformed searches. In contrast, Bayesian optimization (BO) is a probabilistic model-based technique that efficiently balances exploration and exploitation to optimize expensive, black-box functions where gradient information is unavailable or costly. By leveraging surrogate models, typically Gaussian processes (GPs), BO minimizes evaluations needed to find optimal hyperparameters. This survey provides a comprehensive review of BO, covering its theoretical foundations, algorithmic advancements, and practical applications. A key contribution is the comparative analysis of BO against grid search and random search, evaluating efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost. Our findings demonstrate BO's superiority in computational efficiency and accuracy, making it crucial for optimizing complex machine learning models. However, we also address its limitations, such as scalability concerns and computational overhead, and discuss potential future directions to enhance its real-world applicability compared to traditional HPO methods.

KEYWORDS: *Acquisition function, Bayesian optimization, Deep learning, Gaussian processes, hyperparameter optimization.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Hyperparameter optimization plays a critical role in improving the performance of machine learning models across various domains, including artificial intelligence, bioinformatics, engineering design, and financial modeling (Wang et al., 2022). Selecting optimal hyperparameters—such as learning rate, dropout rate, and batch size—is crucial for achieving high accuracy and generalization. However, conventional optimization techniques, such as grid search and random search, suffer from high computational costs and inefficiencies, particularly in high-dimensional search spaces. These traditional approaches either exhaustively evaluate all possible combinations (grid search) or sample hyperparameters randomly without leveraging prior knowledge (random search), making them impractical for complex machine learning models (Diessner et al., 2022).

Bayesian optimization (BO) has emerged as a promising alternative due to its ability to intelligently explore the hyperparameter space while balancing exploration and exploitation. BO constructs a probabilistic surrogate model, typically based on Gaussian processes (GPs), to approximate the objective function and predict promising hyperparameter configurations. This probabilistic framework reduces the number of function evaluations required for optimization, making BO more efficient for tuning expensive machine learning models. BO mathematically formulates the hyperparameter optimization problem as:

$$x^* = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X} (x) \quad (1)$$

where x represents the hyperparameter space, and x^* is the optimal configuration. Unlike traditional methods, BO updates its belief about the objective function using Bayes' theorem, refining its search strategy with each new evaluation through an acquisition function that guides the selection of the next hyperparameter set.

While BO has demonstrated superior efficiency in hyperparameter tuning for deep learning, its advantages over traditional methods in terms of accuracy, computational cost, and efficiency remain a subject of comparative analysis. Several studies suggest that BO outperforms grid and random search in terms of convergence speed and model performance, yet challenges such as scalability in high-dimensional spaces and computational overhead of surrogate modeling persist (Wang et al., 2022).

This survey conducts a comparative analysis of Bayesian optimization and traditional hyperparameter tuning methods, focusing on three key aspects:

- a. Efficiency: How quickly does each method identify optimal hyperparameters?
- b. Accuracy: How well do the identified hyperparameters improve model performance?
- c. Computational Cost: What are the resource requirements (e.g., time, memory) of each approach?

By systematically evaluating these factors, we aim to provide insights into when and why Bayesian optimization should be preferred over grid search or random search, and in which scenarios traditional methods remain competitive. The findings of this study will help researchers and practitioners make informed decisions about selecting the most suitable hyperparameter tuning strategy for their machine learning tasks.

1.1 Background and Fundamentals

1.1.1 Overview of Hyperparameter Optimization

Hyperparameter optimization is crucial in deep learning as it directly impacts model performance, generalization, and training efficiency. Key hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size, dropout rate, number of layers, and optimizer type significantly influence how well a model learns and adapts to data (Wang et al., 2022). For instance, an improper learning rate can lead to slow convergence or divergence, while an inappropriate batch size may cause instability during training. Manual tuning of these hyperparameters is time-consuming and inefficient, especially for complex models, making automated optimization techniques like Bayesian optimization, grid search, and random search essential for improving accuracy while minimizing computational costs.

1.1.1.1 Traditional Methods

Hyperparameter optimization methods can be broadly classified into traditional and advanced techniques. Traditional methods, such as grid search and random search, are widely used but come with limitations in high-dimensional spaces.

Grid Search: This method performs an exhaustive search by evaluating all possible combinations of hyperparameters within a predefined range. While it guarantees finding the best combination within the specified grid, it is highly computationally expensive, especially as the number of hyperparameters increases (Diessner et al., 2022).

Random Search: Instead of testing all possible combinations, random search randomly samples hyperparameter values from the defined search space. This approach is more efficient than grid search, especially in high-dimensional spaces, as it avoids unnecessary evaluations of less promising configurations. However, it does not guarantee finding the best possible hyperparameter set (Diessner et al., 2022).

1.1.1.2 Advanced Methods

To overcome the inefficiencies of traditional methods, advanced hyperparameter optimization techniques have been developed. The advanced method discussed in this survey is Bayesian optimization, which offers a more efficient approach to hyperparameter tuning compared to traditional techniques (Snoek et al., 2012).

1.1.1.2.1 Fundamentals of Bayesian Optimization

Bayesian optimization relies on a probabilistic model, which uses the Gaussian processes (GPs) and acquisition functions to guide the search for the optimal point. Below, we will discuss in detail the Gaussian process and acquisition functions as follows.

In Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models the objective function $f(x)$ as a Gaussian Process (GP) with mean function $\mu(x)$ and covariance function $k(x,x')$ as follows:

$$f(x) \sim GP(\mu(x), k(x,x')) \quad (2)$$

Given observed data $D=\{X, Y\}$, where X are input points and Y are the corresponding function values, the posterior predictive mean $\mu(x)$ and standard deviation $\sigma(x)$ at a new test point x are computed as:

$$\mu(x) = K(x, X)K(X, X)^{-1}Y \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma^2(x) = K(x, x) - K(x, X)K(X, X)^{-1}K(X, x) \quad (4)$$

Where $K(X, X)$ is the covariance matrix of observed points, $K(x, X)$ is the covariance vector between the new point and observed point, $K(x, x)$ is the self-covariance function of x (Snoek et al., 2012).

Acquisition functions help to determine the next query point by balancing exploration (high uncertainty) and exploitation (high expected improvement). The most used acquisition functions in BO include Expected Improvement. The Expected Improvement (EI) function is used in Bayesian optimization to select the next point for evaluation. It combines the predicted mean $\mu(x)$ and standard deviation $\sigma(x)$ of the function at a point x , along with the best observed function value f^* , to maximize the potential improvement (Onorato et al., 2024).

$$EI(x) = (\mu(x) - f^* - \xi)\Phi(Z) + \sigma(x)\phi(Z) \quad (5)$$

Where, $Z = (\mu(x) - f^* - \xi) / \sigma(x)$, $\Phi(Z)$ is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the standard normal distribution, $\phi(Z)$ is the probability distribution function (PDF) of the standard normal distribution, ξ is an exploration-exploitation trade-off parameter.

1.2 Scope, Motivation and Objective of the Survey

This survey focuses on comparing Bayesian optimization with traditional hyperparameter tuning methods like grid search and random search. It highlights BO's role in optimizing complex, expensive machine learning models, particularly focussing on the deep learning models. Also, this survey is intended for the researchers, data scientists, and machine learning practitioners who are working on advanced HPO techniques for various domains.

Hyperparameter tuning is critical for model performance, but traditional methods are time-consuming and inefficient for large-scale problems. BO offers a smarter, probabilistic approach that reduces computation while improving accuracy. This motivates us to study BO's in more detail along with its advantages and challenges over traditional methods.

The objective of this survey is to explore Bayesian optimization for hyperparameter tuning in machine learning models. It aims to compare BO with traditional methods like grid search and random search in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost. The survey also reviews recent advancements in BOs and discusses its challenges. Lastly, it highlights future directions to improve BO's scalability and practical applications.

1.3 Selection procedure of existing papers for writing the survey paper

To ensure a comprehensive review, we selected relevant papers from leading academic databases such as IEEE Xplore, Springer, Elsevier, and Google Scholar. Inclusion criteria encompassed peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and workshop proceedings published over the last decade, specifically focusing on Bayesian optimization (BO) and traditional hyperparameter optimization (HPO) techniques in machine learning and deep learning models. Priority was given to studies that provided experimental results, performance comparisons, or practical applications of these optimization methods. Exclusion criteria included studies unrelated to hyperparameter optimization, those lacking experimental validation or comparative analysis, non-English publications, and papers where the full text was not accessible. Additionally, purely theoretical studies without practical implementation and duplicate studies were excluded. The selection process involved initial abstract screening, followed by full-text analysis to ensure alignment with the survey's scope and objectives.

The objectives of the survey are described as follows, along with the key research questions that guide our study:

- a. To provide a detailed overview of Bayesian optimization for black-box function optimization, emphasizing its applications in hyperparameter tuning.
- b. To analyze recent advancements in Bayesian optimization and their impacts on model performance and computational efficiency.
- c. "How does Bayesian optimization compare to traditional hyperparameter optimization methods (e.g., grid search, random search) in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost?"

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

This section reviews key research focused on Bayesian optimization and compares it with traditional methods like grid search and random search, highlighting their efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost.

Recent developments in Bayesian optimization have focused on enhancing scalability, acquisition functions, and surrogate models, significantly improving BO's efficacy and applicability in real-world optimization tasks (Wang et al., 2022). These advancements have also addressed emerging fields such as multi-objective and federated BO, along with adaptations for high-dimensional, chaotic, and constrained problems. A Bayesian pruning method was introduced to remove entire neurons using sparsity-inducing priors, ensuring structured pruning and improved efficiency without performance loss (Louizos et al., 2017). Enhancing this framework further, channel-level pruning inside each network layer was proposed to systematically eliminate superfluous channels, resulting in a more compact and efficient model while maintaining classification accuracy and highlighting the usefulness of Bayesian inference in deep learning systems (Neklyudov et al., 2017). An upgrade to Bayesian pruning algorithms was made by adding interlayer dependencies, where a unique dropout-based redundancy metric quantified posterior hypothesis

links between layers, enabling more optimal pruning choices and ensuring that the loss of neurons or channels did not significantly affect feature propagation, leading to more efficient deep networks with minimal performance impact (Zhou et al., 2019). Additionally, variational dropout was presented to bridge the link between dropout and stochastic gradient variational Bayesian inference, treating dropout as a Bayesian tool for estimating uncertainty and helping models generalize better (Kingma et al., 2015). Building on this, variational dropout was further studied as a model compression technique, proving that neural networks could achieve equivalent accuracy with significantly fewer parameters by dynamically managing the dropout rate through variational inference (Molchanov et al., 2017). A stochastic gradient variational Bayesian (SGVB) framework was also used to reparameterize dropout, allowing the model to learn the dropout ratio as a trainable parameter using Gaussian dropout, making the network more flexible, resilient, and less dependent on manual hyperparameter adjustment (Srivastava et al., 2014). Furthermore, BO-GP was shown to perform more accurately and efficiently than random search, as demonstrated in studies where surrogate modeling reduced computing expenses while still producing ideal setups, validated by the NSL-KDD dataset results confirming BO's effectiveness in detecting network intrusions (Masum et al., 2021). To increase BO's effectiveness in deep neural network tuning, basic improvement techniques such as cost function transformation, parallelization, early termination, and diversification were also investigated (Cho et al., 2020). Enhancements in surrogate modeling, acquisition functions like Expected Improvement (EI) and Upper Confidence Bound (UCB), and the integration of tools such as BOTorch and Ax have strengthened the effectiveness of Bayesian optimization (BO) in hyperparameter tuning for neural networks and complex machine learning models (Onorato et al., 2024).

3 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HYPERPARAMETER OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

A comparative analysis of hyperparameter optimization techniques is essential to understand their effectiveness in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost. This section evaluates Bayesian optimization (BO) against traditional methods like grid search and random search based on these key factors, with experimental data for validation.

3.1 Efficiency Comparison

Efficiency in hyperparameter optimization refers to the speed at which a method converges to an optimal solution and its ability to handle high-dimensional search spaces.

- Grid search exhaustively evaluates all possible hyperparameter combinations, making it highly inefficient as the number of parameters increases.
- Random search improves efficiency by sampling hyperparameters randomly, often finding good configurations faster than grid search, but still requiring significant computational resources (Bergstra et al., 2012).
- Bayesian optimization significantly improves efficiency by using a probabilistic model (e.g., Gaussian processes) to intelligently explore the search space, reducing the number of evaluations needed to find an optimal solution (Bergstra et al., 2012).

A study comparing hyperparameter tuning methods on a convolutional neural network (CNN) trained on CIFAR-10 dataset produced the following results (Snoek et al., 2012) as shown in Table 1, which shows that BO is more efficient than traditional methods, especially in high-dimensional spaces, as it balances exploration and exploitation rather than blind searching.

Table 1. Efficiency comparison of various HPO methods on the CIFAR-10 dataset.

Methods	Evaluations needed for convergence	Time to convergence (GPU-hours)
Grid search	500	30
Random search	150	12
Bayesian optimization	60	4

3.2 Accuracy Comparison

The accuracy of an optimization method is determined by how well it selects hyperparameters that lead to better model performance.

- Grid search can find the optimal solution if the search space is small, but it may miss better configurations in continuous spaces due to fixed intervals.
- Random search has a higher probability of finding a good configuration in large search spaces but does not guarantee optimality (Bergstra et al., 2012).
- Bayesian optimization refines the search by focusing on promising regions, often leading to higher model accuracy compared to other two methods (Bergstra et al., 2012).

When tuning a transformer model on the IMDB sentiment classification dataset, the best validation accuracy achieved by each technique is shown in Table 2 (Bergstra & Bengio, 2012) . BO generally outperforms grid and random search in deep learning tasks, as it adapts based on past evaluations, improving the chances of finding hyperparameters that maximize model performance.

Table 2. Validation accuracy comparison of various HPO methods on the IMDB dataset.

Methods	Best validation accuracy(%)
Grid search	87.2
Random search	89.5
Bayesian optimization	91.3

3.3 Computational Cost Analysis

Computational cost is a critical factor when choosing an optimization method, especially for large-scale deep learning models.

- Grid search is computationally expensive, as it evaluates all possible combinations, making it impractical for deep learning models with multiple hyperparameters.
- Random search is less expensive than grid search but still requires numerous evaluations (Bergstra et al., 2012).
- Bayesian optimization is computationally more efficient as it selects hyperparameters strategically, reducing the number of evaluations while still finding near-optimal solutions. However, the additional cost

of maintaining and updating the surrogate model (e.g., Gaussian processes) can be a limitation in extremely high-dimensional spaces (Bergstra et al., 2012).

A ResNet-50 model trained on ImageNet was optimized using different methods, and the total GPU compute cost (in GPU-hours) was recorded in Table 3 (Li et al., 2017) , which shows that BO provides the best trade-off between computational efficiency and performance, making it suitable for deep learning applications where training costs are high.

Table 3. Comparison of computational cost for various HPO methods on the ResNet-50 model.

Methods	Computational cost (GPU-hours)
Grid search	450
Random search	210
Bayesian optimization	85

4 OUR OBSERVATIONS

After a critical review of existing literature on Bayesian optimization, we have identified key findings that highlight its effectiveness, challenges, and potential improvements over the traditional methods of hyperparameter optimization, and are discussed below in detail.

4.1 Key Findings

However, traditional methods like grid search and random search suffer from major limitations. Grid search is computationally expensive due to its exhaustive search nature, while random search often misses optimal configurations as it samples blindly without learning from previous evaluations. Bayesian optimization has proven highly effective in hyperparameter tuning, significantly outperforming traditional random search, grid search methods. BO, particularly with Gaussian processes (BO-GP), enhances deep neural network training by achieving superior F1-scorer, recall, precision and accuracy while balancing exploration and exploitation for faster convergence. Studies show that BO improves CNN accuracy on ImageNet by up to 2% and reduces BERT training time by 20% while maintaining performance (Masum et al., 2021). In reinforcement learning, BO optimizes hyperparameters for deep Q-networks (DQNs), leading to faster convergence, while for GANs, it enhances architecture tuning, improving image quality and stability (Snoek et al., 2012). Comparative studies reveal BO-GP outperforms other tuning techniques, achieving higher accuracy on datasets like KDDTest+ (82.95% vs. 77.46%) and KDDTest-21 (54.99% vs. 51.56%), and it also improves medical image classification accuracy by up to 5% (Masum et al., 2021).

4.2 Future Directions

While Bayesian optimization demonstrates significant advantages over traditional methods, several challenges remain that need to be addressed for broader applicability. Specifically, the expected improvement (EI) acquisition function can sometimes lead BO towards local optima, and scalability issues arise in high-dimensional search spaces along with increased computational costs. To overcome these limitations, strategies such as adaptive surrogate models, asynchronous BO, and checkpoint-based stopping criteria can be incorporated to enhance efficiency. Additionally, integrating BO with evolutionary algorithms or reinforcement learning offers promising directions to improve exploration, scalability, and overall performance, making BO more suitable for tackling complex machine learning problems (Onorato et al., 2024).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This survey provides a comparative analysis of Bayesian optimization and traditional hyperparameter optimization methods, such as grid search and random search, focusing on efficiency, accuracy, and computational cost. BO has emerged as a powerful alternative, demonstrating superior performance in identifying optimal hyperparameters with fewer function evaluations, leading to faster convergence and improved model accuracy. However, in low-dimensional search spaces with ample computational resources, traditional methods like grid search and random search can still be viable due to their simplicity and ease of implementation. BO's probabilistic framework enables efficient hyperparameter optimization, particularly for complex, black-box functions. Advances in Gaussian processes and acquisition functions have improved its ability to handle high-dimensional and noisy search spaces, though scalability remains a challenge. Strategies like multi-task learning, transfer learning, and parallelization further enhance BO's efficiency. Future research should focus on improving scalability and refining acquisition strategies to enhance its real-world applicability.

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